

Adoption of Blockchain Technology Framework for Addressing Counterfeit Drugs Circulation

Ohis G. Mega

Department of Computer Science, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria

Maureen I. Akazue

Department of Computer Science, Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria

Oghenevovwero Zion Apene

Centre for Satellite Technology Development, National Space Research and Development Agency, Abuja, Nigeria

JohnPaul A.C. Hampo

Department of Computer Science, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

More Information

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Abstract

Counterfeit drugs are a problem both in developed and developing countries. Nigeria is a developing country experiencing the problem of counterfeit drugs and as such is the use case for this research work. The negative effects counterfeit drugs have on human health and economy of the country calls for urgent attention. One amongst many reasons why counterfeit drugs are still in circulation in Nigeria is the unmonitored drug distribution system. Drugs throughout their shelf life moves from one owner to another, from the importer/manufacturer to Distributor, wholesaler to government/private healthcare sectors and then to the patients. The current drug distribution system in Nigeria is a manually, unmonitored system, where the regulatory agency body National Agency for Food and Drug Administration control (NAFDAC) does not have detailed record on the movement of drugs from either the importer or manufacturer to the patient in the system. In this study blockchain technology framework that can handle the drug distribution chain was discussed, since blockchain technology offers immutability, transparency and tamper proof, its functionalities are what intrigued the study as it can help monitor the movement of drug in the distribution chain. The proposed system is a prototype demonstrating the hashing mechanism with a deployed smart contract and how it can help in showing the authenticity of a drug. The blockchain framework is a private blockchain, where participants on the network are permitted to have access to the network by the regulatory agency. The system was evaluated based on its effectiveness from users reports using the security, user friendly, response time, flexibility, data integrity checks, robust, hashing mechanism functional as the benchmark. The actual test result equates the expected test result, showing that the system is efficient.

Introduction

Background Information

In recent years there have been an increasing number of cutting-edge technologies. One of such is Blockchain Technology. Blockchain technology came into existence as a result of the need to secure digital financial data transactions to eliminate the third party, creating transparency in all transactions and making the

transaction immutable [1]. Blockchain is a peer-to-peer network that holds ledgers in a distributed format, thereby making it immutable [1]. However, over the years, the applicability of blockchain technology to several fields has risen, though still in its infant stage, blockchain has attracted attention from different industries such as real estate [2], agriculture [3], drug

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Tracking [4], energy management system [5], drug supply management system [6] etc.

Blockchain technological principle uses specialized algorithms and other new technologies to authenticate and validate transactions within a decentralized architecture although progressing in real-time through protected layers of digital encryption. The blockchain promotes security [7], thereby making it impossible to hack from outside except by the miners. An example of the technology it employs in the distributed ledger is the use of hashgraph software. Hashgraph software addresses the scalability issues of traditional distributed ledger technology (DLT) [8].

Miners are people that calculate the hash value for proceeding blocks [9]. Data that can be hashed into a blockchain range from transaction information, images, videos, and other design files [8]. The blocks of a blockchain contain metadata such as references of the previous work, a proof-of-work which is also called a

nonce, and a tree for transactions known as the Merkle tree, and a timestamp [10].

Drugs regulation in Nigeria is done by the National Agency for Food and Drugs Administration and Control (NAFDAC). This agency which is a parastatal of the Federal Ministry of Health, was established in January 1993 by Ibrahim Babangida, the then Head of State (Military President). NAFDAC regulates and controls the production, exportation, importation, distribution, advertisement, sales and use of food, drugs, cosmetics, chemicals and detergents, medical devices and all drinks, including packaged and bottled water [11]

Literature Review

Different types of blockchain framework have been proposed since it's emergency. [12] put forward a system that can tighten the security of the flow of drugs and patients health data within a smart hospital in order to prevent counterfeit drugs from having access into the distribution chain.

Figure 1: Architecture of the Proposed Drug Distribution Chain Management System [12]

[13], [6] proposed a blockchain-based framework to exterminate drug counterfeiting. Similarly, [14] proposed a blockchain-Internet of things (IoT) supply chain network for COVID-19, also [15] suggested the use of blockchain technology to combat counterfeit drugs using a mobile app. [16] proposed the use of the blockchain Ethereum platform with the smart contract and storing data off-chain in solving the issues faced in the healthcare supply chain after investigating the pharmaceutical supply chain.

Blockchain in Healthcare System

[17] emphasized the need for blockchain technology to be adopted in healthcare while [18] surveyed to know the areas where blockchain can be more useful in healthcare and how best to implement it.

Blockchain Technology in Other Supply Chain Management System

Blockchain mechanism is a new and evolving technology with capabilities of solving issues faced with

in the distribution chain system as established by [15], [16], [17] and [18].

Drug Distribution System in Nigeria

The drug distribution system in Nigeria is in an apologetic state that needs reform as pointed out in their study by [19], [20].

Anti-Counterfeit Measures in Nigeria

The measures that have been put in place to curb counterfeit drugs circulation in Nigeria are conversed in the following paragraph.

The conception of the national drug policy [21] and the establishment of National Agency for Food and Drug Administration Control (NAFDAC) with the introduction of NAFDAC registration number [22]. NAFDAC also employed the use of technologies as discussed by [23] and [24] discussed the issues affecting the use of mobile authentication system (MAS) and the technology on which the MAS is built on as the unstructured supplementary service data (USSD) and the short message service (SMS), pointing out that the

mechanism is not 100% effective and stated some reasons why as follows; partial implementation among drug manufacturers, poor network, unawareness amongst others. Radio Frequency Identification System, Truscan is based on an image recognition algorithm [24], Global Pharma Health Fund Minilab Test Kit (GPHF) is a mini-lab chemical test kit [25], The Black Eye is similar to Tru-Scan, but works with the principle of active thermography [26].

Counterfeit Drug Circulation in Nigeria

The evidence of counterfeit drugs in circulation were stated in the study conducted by [27], [28], [29], [15]. This proved that despite the efforts to curb counterfeit drugs circulation, it still thrives. Hence, adopting Blockchain technology in the winning the exhausting fight against counterfeit drug circulation will go a long way.

Figure 2: Use Case of the System Application [14]

Materials and Methods

The proposed system is a drug distribution system that uses a private blockchain framework, since a private blockchain is permitted to be redesigned to meet the prerequisites of an organization and following the ease of configuring it to suit the request of participants in an organizational setting. And was developed by adopting the software methodology Rapid Application Development Model known as the RAD technique. The reason why this was chosen over others is because, RAD offers quick delivery of proposed software, using prototypes at various levels of iteration considering the user’s feedback and is appropriate for developing software within a short period where the goal of the system is to develop the task corresponding to the users’ requirements [30].

Analysis of The Existing System

According to [20], the existing drug distribution system in Nigeria is a manual system with no proper record-keeping information, also [19] stated categorically that the drug distribution system structure in Nigeria is a flounder, with the present system operating as a manual system. The existing drug distribution system has multiple importers/manufacturers that take

demand from multiple wholesalers in the open drug market, following this same order different government healthcare facilities, private hospitals, pharmacies go to buy drugs from multiple wholesalers in the open drug markets, who eventually sell the drug to the patients.

The drugs move to the market after the NAFDAC number has been awarded and the processes of buying and selling is immediately initialized until it gets to the patients.

a) **NAFDAC:** As the government drug and food regulating agency in charge of verifying the genuineness of the drug in Nigeria, NAFDAC approves a number called the NAFDAC number on the drug that are both imported and manufactured in Nigeria, and also give the manufacturer and importer the go-ahead to use the SMS authentication system. With approval to sell the drugs.

b) **IMPORTER/MANUFACTURER:** These importers and manufacturers then sell their drugs in the open drug market to wholesalers.

c) **WHOLESALE:** Wholesalers in turn buy drugs from multiple and diverse importers and manufacturers, then they sell these drugs in the open

drug markets to both federal and state government healthcare facilities and retailers. These retailers are private healthcare facilities, pharmacies, and chemist stores.

Figure 3: Flowchart of the Existing Drug Distribution System

d) **GOVERNMENT HEALTHCARE FACILITIES/PRIVATE HEALTHCARE FACILITIES:** The government healthcare facilities both at the federal and state levels, private healthcare facilities, pharmacies, and chemist stores all goes to the open drug markets to buy drugs from wholesalers and then sells directly to the patients.

e) **PATIENTS/CUSTOMERS:** These patients buy drugs from pharmacies, chemist stores, or get drugs from private hospitals and government healthcare facilities for use when they are sick.

Weaknesses of The Existing System

1. The existing system has the following weaknesses:
2. The existing system operates manually
3. The existing system has no database that keeps records of all the participants involved in the process of drug circulation
4. The existing system does not keep records of the flow of drugs along the distribution chain.
5. The existing system is an open drug market without a verification process by the participants involved in the distribution of the drugs.
6. The process of drug distribution in the existing system is nontransparent. The existing system does not have records of drugs circulated by the legitimate participant.

Figure 4. Architecture the Existing Drug Distribution System in Nigeria

Analysis of The Proposed System

The Proposed Drug Distribution System in Nigeria Since the existing drug flow system in Nigeria starts with NAFDAC, awarding the NAFDAC number that is inscribed on the drugs, despite NAFDAC not having documentation of the entire drugs in the public market.

The proposed system using a blockchain technology framework will start with NAFDAC verifying and uploading the drug information onto the blockchain community. NAFDAC will be the one in charge of the blockchain network maintenance. NAFDAC relates with different importers and manufacturers and therefore is

in charge of grouping the participant in the network. A route is then created where one or more group is attached to a defined route of transaction. These groups include all the participants in the community, with each of the groups having a link at each level in the community. The information and transactions at each of the levels are recorded with the previous hash of the last transaction and information.

The drug distribution system is the same as the drug supply chain system, which will involve all relevant parties in the drug business in Nigeria. These participants include the following: NAFDAC, Importers, Manufacturers, Distributors, Private healthcare facilities, Government healthcare facilities, etc. The drug distribution system may be called Nafchain. Nafchain is a private permissioned drug distribution network, that allows only verified participants to have access either to read or write centered on the privilege granted. The write access allows the participants to create a transaction with each other while the read

access allows information accessibility whenever needed. Nafchain is a drug distribution system that adopts technology behind blockchain to build a see-through and traceable distribution system, that allows the input of data, storing of data, monitoring, and sharing of information, and the overall management of activities within the system network.

The proposed system uses a smart contract and validating node is selected based on the set of rules stated by the smart contract.

The components that make up the Nafchain are consensus algorithm, drug distribution participants, smart contracts, permissions, transactions, and database. For every participant invited to join the network, Nafchain issues a digital certificate with a special identity number (ID) and key pair. This special ID number is mandatory when verifying the identity of a participant that is requesting the write access.

Figure 5 shows the decentralized network constructed on the information accessible on the network.

Figure 5: Architecture of Blockchain-Based Decentralized Network

Advantages of The Proposed System

1. The proposed system eliminates the open drug market system.
2. The proposed system is an automated system.
3. The proposed system is transparent to every participant on the network.
4. The proposed system support information traceability.
5. The proposed system is tamper proof.
6. The proposed system will help to curb counterfeit drugs circulation in Nigeria.

High-Level Model of The Proposed System

a) Participants: The participants are the members of the blockchain network, with the patient

and they can only access the network through the use of a software application with a front-end. Depending on the access assigned to each participant. The participant can either initiate a transaction, validate it, or read-only. For example, patients only have read access and the only information they can access is the drug history

b) Software technologies: The software technology utilized in the design of the Application backend and front end include python programming language, Flask framework for web on Python programming language, HTML, and Bootstrap a CSS framework. The participants with transaction access achieve that with the smart contract.

- c) Smart Contracts: A smart contract is a set of policies governing the activities on the blockchain community and it is initiated when certain requirements are met. The smart contract is in charge of the hashes in the transaction process and monitors them in the decentralized data storage. It is within the smart contract the positions of all the participants in the network are defined using a modifier. A modifier is used to checkmate a written contract.
- d) Decentralized Data Storage: This is the information of all the transactions stored in form of a block in a blockchain on the different nodes peered together the blockchain network. The information stored within the decentralized data storage must have met all the smart contract prerequisites and been validated.
- e)

Figure 6: A High-Level Model of the Proposed of the Proposed System

Architecture of blockchain Framework

A. NODE PEERING

Node peering are computers connected on the blockchain network to form peering and are used for processing transactions. They obey the smart contract defined within the community. They carry out all the transactional activities on the network depending on all privileges granted to them. The main participant on the network is recommended to host the peering of the system. This is because developing and maintaining the system involves a large amount. All other participants can simply access the blockchain network through an application on a compatible device. The validation and

approval of a transaction can be done based on the selected peers as defined by the consensus mechanism.

B. APPLICATIONS

Applications are software interfaces that are user-friendly that serve as a link to the blockchain network. These applications support the use of multiple devices to connect to the blockchain network concurrently by different participants and also support the access of the same participant on multiple devices founded on the permission granted. These applications can be defined at different levels, each of which serves its purpose. It could either be for the posting of information on the blockchain or for reading existing data logs on the network.

C. ROUTES

Routes are the design of separately defined smart contracts at different levels of transaction. That is a route designed for a type of transaction, for example, either for a financial transaction or for a product transaction. This supports the confidentiality of records at various accessibility levels. For every participant in the community, the basic law governing the entire blockchain network must be obeyed, while the law governing the particular route they want to access must also be obeyed.

D. PROGRAM CONTROL

Program control is the block information collection algorithm that keeps the rule that chains every block together in the system functioning. It regulates the entire activities on the block in the blockchain community by gathering information of a particular transaction of a participant on the network and arranging them into a block for validation. After the validation process, the ordering service appends the block to the last block in the blockchain network of the route where the transaction occurred.

E. MEMBERSHIP SERVICE OPERATIONS

The key pair is what makes blockchain that is private secure and trustworthy. The pair of keys are generated by the participating services. the pairing of the keys is in the structure of a public-private key and they are centered on the accessibility rights of the participants in the community. A unique key pair is generated for every supply chain system that employs a blockchain that is private.

Figure 7 illustrates how the proposed blockchain framework works. NAFDAC creates the blockchain and hosts the different routes on which the nodes in the various groups can transact. The different routes are created with rules governing the entire network (Rc) and rules governing specific routes (R1 and R2). In figure 7 only two routes (Route 1 and Route 2) were created for two groups (group1 and group2) to allow the participants in the various groups to interact with each other. The different nodes peer (NP) on the different route hosts the smart contract(S) and

distributed ledger (DL). The nodes peer (NP1 and NP2) are linked to route (R1 and R2) and initiating smart contracts (S1 and S2) and distributed ledger (DL1 and DL2), with node system peering (Ns) having access to host both smart contracts (S1 and S2) and distributed ledger (DL1 and DL2) on routes (R1 and R2). Applications are developed with different permission

right, Sys1a, Sys1b, and Sys2a, Sys2b has access to route 1 and route 2 respectively, APR is an application with permission to access both route 1 and route 2, while PAA is the application developed for the patient only with permission to the read-only part of the drug along the distribution chain, and serves as a verification system in other to trace the origin of the drugs.

Figure 7: Architecture of Blockchain Framework for Drug Distribution in Nigeria

Note: DL-Distributed shared ledger; NP-Node peer are systems peered together on the network; PC-Program control Sys-Application built to communicate with the blockchain network; 1-represents route 1; 2-represent route 2; R-rule governing a particular route; Rc- rule governing all the routes in the network; S-smart contract; Ns-node system peering with permission to multiple routes; PAA-patient with application to access the blockchain network; APR-Application with permission to access multiple routes

The Mode of Information Sharing

1. For a system implementing a blockchain technology framework, the information-sharing model is paramount. This is because blockchain transactions are transparent, nevertheless, not all information should be made public due to security risks. Considering the drug distribution system in Nigeria, it is risky to make all the records available to the patients which are the consumers. This is because 1) fraudsters can pose as patients just to get into the system. 2) the patients only check the veracity of the drugs; in order words, the patients are not part of the distribution chain. Hence only limited information should be shared. Based on this principle, the proposed blockchain framework for drug distribution in Nigeria follows the information sharing system proposed by (Kumar et al., 2017) to divide the information sharing

into two groups with the aim to reduce the complexity of the mode of sharing such information. They are

2. Private Information - Private information is a protected information that is accessible to the only authorized group and the seller of the drug. Since they are delicate and confidential information, that when it falls into wrong hands can cause great havoc, such as the IP data and the financial information of the participants on the network.
3. Shareable Information - Shareable information is the information that is accessible to both the buyer, the entire participants on the network, and the patient.
4. Though this information is separated into other to access them for security reasons yet, they have certain keys that link both together. This group of information was referred to by Kumar et al., (2017) as linking information.

5. Linking Information - The linking information plays a crucial task in the transaction that is conceded on the blockchain network. The smart contract uses it to connect every transaction to the distributed shared ledger. This is so because this information is used in the confirmation process, checking to see if the smart contract conditions are met with the linking information connecting to the distributed shared ledger. The four components that make up the linking information are:

6. The Public Key is used to supervise the identities of every participant on the network. This is so because it is used to verify the transaction initiated by a participant against the shared ledger for checking if the initiator of such transaction is a greater or equal asset to the transaction initiated.

7. Transactional Signature is used for creating a transaction by the participant on the network and is made up of both the private key and the unique ID generated for the specific participants.

8. Traceability ID is a major for tracking assets on the blockchain community. And it is generated only by NAFDAC for the asset of either the manufacturer or importer.

9. Asset Value is the measure of digital information on a product owned by the community participant used for the transaction after NAFDAC must have tested and approved the drug for sale.

The Blockchain Framework Inbuilt Requirements

This section discusses the conditions required for developing the proposed system:

Permissions

Following the prerequisites in a private blockchain, the membership service provider issues a unique ID to every participant on the blockchain community. Also, a public-private key pair is generated and used for authentication on the system. The unique ID of each participant is connected to the public key of that particular participant on the network and this can be used as criteria to grant privileges to participants on the network.

Smart Contract

Two algorithms peculiar to the distribution system are centered on two aspects of a participant's account. The first algorithm checks the details of the participant engaging in a transaction to know if, the initiating participant has the required asset to be transacted. This algorithm uses the account balancing method. While the second algorithm is based on the inventory details of every asset on the blockchain. This method also uses the account balancing method. This account balancing method was preferred to other methods since, it is

faster in systems with multiple participants having multiple assets available for transaction on the blockchain network.

The smart contract is designed to be deployed when a product is to be registered for the first time by the system admin and then every subsequent transaction on the product.

When applying the account balancing method to the drug distribution system manufacturing participants, a manufacturer can have a license to produce different types of drugs that would definitely have different NAFDAC numbers and possibly be bought by different wholesalers. Here the account balancing method used in the smart contract would permit the blockchain to be able to trace the origin of every asset on the blockchain. This is because the account denotes to the details of every participant on the network and transaction denotes to every transaction ever made on the network.

Consensus Algorithm

The Proof of Authority (PoA) consensus Barinov et al., (2018) as cited in [32] is considered for the confirmation of the transaction to be referred to as a block and then affixed to the last block on the blockchain network. The reason PoA is used is that the validating nodes are trusted and known nodes on the network. Based on this phenomenon the network tends to centralization. For the nodes in the community, the initiating peer participating in the transaction creates the transaction, the accepting peer then agrees to the transaction and the regulatory body validates the transaction for it to be affixed to the blockchain. The validated transaction becomes a block containing the information of the hash of the previous block, block id, transaction details. The prototype of the proposed system was developed to only part of the working system. Though the system suggested was developed on a single computer system.

Transactions

The transactions in the proposed system contain the distribution process of drugs and the transaction information in the distribution system by different participants on multiple channels and at different levels. Based on the fact that there can be multiple participants on the same level and transacting on different routes. Multiple manufacturers, manufacturing different types of drugs and multiple imports, importing different types of drugs, and all these drugs must pass through NAFDAC for testing and verification of the genuineness of the drugs. For this explanation, the developed prototype of the proposed system is explained diagrammatically in figure 8.

Figure 8: Architecture of the Transactional Flow Diagram

The above diagram in figure 8 depicts the transaction engaged by various participants at various levels. NAFDAC is the first to upload the information of the drug onto the blockchain network, thereby creating the first block and subsequently transferring the right of initiating transaction either to the manufacturer or the importer, and in turn, these importers or manufacturers transacts with the subordinate level until it gets to the hospital or pharmacy where the patient get their drugs.

After NAFDAC verifies the drug authenticity and after uploading the first block, which is the genesis block is hashed, the right to initiate transaction then goes to either the manufacturer or the importer. For demonstration purposes on the proposed drug distribution system only the manufacturers/importer unique ID, with username and password was used.

Then the smart contract checks if the initiating participants are authorized participants with the necessary asset requirement for the transaction that has been initiated. If this returns true, then permission is granted and the receiving participant accepts the products and then the second block is hashed which is block 1. This process continues the distribution chain as the transaction continues from the higher level to the lower level.

To demonstrate the application of the blockchain framework, a program written in python 3.9, HTML, and Flask (a python light web framework) was written on an Intel (R) Core (TM) i5-43100, CPU 2.00 GHZ with memory 4.00 GB running on windows 10 pro. The designed blockchain framework is a prototype exhibiting only the hash condition that uses MD-5 encryption.

Figure 9: Architecture of the Proposed NAFCHAIN Drug Distribution System

1. **NAFDAC:** NAFDAC is the sole admin of the system. NAFDAC invites other participants to NAFCHAIN and grants privileges to participants depending on the priority. NAFDAC uploads information of the verified drugs to the blockchain, the hash of the block, date approved, timestamps are then created and then sends the physical drugs back to either the importer/manufacturer for distribution, then based on the smart contracts, the new block is validated for it to be appended to the blockchain. The following are the essential components of the drug distribution chain system; the drug distribution participants, permissions, smart contracts, consensus algorithm, and transactions.

2. **DRUG DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM PARTICIPANTS**
 3. **NAFDAC:** is the regulatory body and the only certified participant of the community that is allowed to upload the first transactional data of the physically verified drug thereby creating the first block in the network. For every other transaction in the network, NAFDAC is charged with validating the transaction before the new block is appended. Also, for every block the transactional evidence of the two participants is captured and kept in the block.

4. **IMPORTER/MANUFACTURER:** broadcasts the verified drugs for orders by the wholesalers and government healthcare facilities, take orders, and sends the physical drugs to the distributors for distributing to specified wholesaler and government healthcare facility. And, uploads the transactional information to the network for validation by NAFDAC

5. **DISTRIBUTOR:** takes orders of drugs to be dispersed from the importer/manufacturer to the specified wholesaler and government healthcare facility. Then transport the physical drug to the location of the specified recipients. Uploads the transactional information for validation by NAFDAC.

6. **WHOLEALER/GOVERNMENT HEALTHCARE FACILITY:** places order for drugs to the importer/manufacturer, receives physical drugs from the distributor, uploads transactional information for validation. Then wholesaler broadcast available drugs on the community for order.

7. **PHARMACY/PRIVATE HEALTHCARE FACILITY:** orders from the list of broadcasted drugs on the network and uploads the transactional information for validation.

8. **PATIENTS/CONSUMER:** A verification system is agreed upon by NAFDAC and the importer/manufacturer to be used by the consumer for checking the veracity of the drugs. The patient access to the community will simply be to read drug record information as shown below.

Figure 10: Block Diagram of Patients Querying the Blockchain

Figure 11: NAFCHAIN Dashboard

The home page is the home interface of the application system in figure 11.

Figure 12: Registration Page

The registration page is the page for registering new user.

Figure 13: Login Page

The login page is used by already registered users to access the application as shown in figure13.

Figure 14: Block Entry Page of the Prototype Drug Distribution System

Figure 14 is the interface for entering information forming a block.

Figure 15: Integrity Check Page of the Prototype Drug Distribution System

Figure 15 is the frontend for the integrity check page

Figure 16: Backend of the Prototype System

Figure 16 is the back end of the application software.

Figure 17: Frontend Showing the Tampered Block

Figure 17 is the front-end of the application showing that a block has been tampered.

Figure 18. Backend Showing the Tampered Block

Figure 18 is the back-end of the application software showing that block 3 and block 4 has been tampered.

System Specification

1. The system specification are the tools used in the development of the application software, that is the hardware and operating system/ An Intel (R) Core (TM) i5-43100, CPU 2.00 GHZ with memory 4.00 GB running on windows 10 pro was used in the development of the application.
2. Database Development Tool
3. The database tool used is SQLAlchemy. SQLAlchemy is an open-source SQL toolkit and object-relational mapper for the Python programming language.
4. Database Design and structure

Table 1: Database Design and Structure

Fields	Datatype	Size
Username	text	30
password_hash	text	200
email_address	Text	50
user_id	text	random

Table 1 is showing the database design and structured used. The fields, datatypes and size used in creating the database.

1. Program Module Specification

2. The program module specification is functions written in python codes in the python file on visual studio codes.
3. Input/Output Format
4. The input format is text, while the output format is text and graphical.
5. Algorithm

- Step1: begin
 Step2: Create a python file
 Step3: create a virtual environment
 Step4: Activate the virtual environment
 Step5: install flask in a virtual environment, flask_sqlalchemy
 Step 6: Create a file for the flask application
 Step7: import flask, render_template, redirect, request, sqlalchemy in 6
 Step8: create different routes and functions in 6
 Step9: create folder templates
 Step10: create HTML files in 9
 Step11: link HTML files in 10 to routes in 9
 Step12: Create a python file main and import flask_sqlalchemy
 Step13: create a database
 Step14: Create a table named user in 13
 Step15: link database to flask app
 Step16: login into nafchain
 (a) Is login credentials valid, if yes goto 17
 (b) else go to 15
 Step17: is user == NAFDAC
 Then register other participants (importer, manufacturer, government healthcare facilities, etc), grant participants access, verify drugs, validate the transaction
 Step18: else is user == importer/manufacturer

- Then broadcast verified drugs, issue transaction, broadcasted transaction for validation
 Step19: else is user == distributor
 Then distribute drugs to specified participants by importer/manufacturer, check the integrity of drugs
 Step20: else is user == wholesaler
 Then check drug integrity, issue transactions to government healthcare facilities, private healthcare facilities, private healthcare facilities, retailers
 Step21: end

Flow Chart of the Application System

The flowchart in figure 19 describes how the system works. the system starts and is initialized. The participant on the system that are restricted can only check the integrity of the drugs, while those not restricted can perform transactions and also check the integrity of the drug. When a drug integrity is being checked, the system returns requested information and then ends.

Figure 19: Application System Flowchart

RESULTS

In order to study the effectiveness of the proposed system, the following bench mark was considered; security, user friendly, response time, flexibility, data integrity checks, robust, hashing mechanism functional.

Figure 20: Evaluation Result on the System Security

Figure 21: Evaluation Result on the System Usability

Figure 25: Evaluation on the System Robustness

Figure 22: Evaluation Result on the System Response Time

Figure 26. Evaluation on the System Hashing Mechanism Functionality

Figure 23: Evaluation on the System Flexibility

Figure 24: Evaluation on the System Data Integrity Check Effectiveness

The test criteria are as follows: Is the system secure, Is the system user friendly, is the response time fast, Is the system flexible, Is the data integrity check effective, Is the application robust, Is the hashing mechanism functional.

100 questionnaires were administered to 100 users considering the test criteria which are security, usability, response time, flexibility, data integrity check effectiveness, robustness and the functionality of the hashing mechanism.

Figure 20 answered the question on the system security collated from 100 users and showed that 90% of the users agreed that the system is secure, while 5% said the system is not secure, the remaining 5% was undecided.

Figure 21 answered the question on the system usability collated from 100 users and showed that 95% of the users agreed that the system is user friendly while 2% disagreed and the remaining 3% was undeceive.

Figure 22 answered the question on the system response time collated from 100 users and showed that 98% agreed that the system response time is fast, while 1% disagreed and the other 1% was undeceive.

Figure 23 answered the question on the flexibility of the system collated from 100 users and showed that 100% agreed that the system is flexible while there was none disagreeing and no undeceive answer.

Figure 24 answered the question on the data integrity check effectiveness of the system collated from 100 users and showed that 97% agreed that the data integrity check of the system is effective while none disagreed, 3% was undeceive.

Figure 25 answered the question on the robustness of the system collated from 100 users and showed that 95% agreed that the system is robust, 1% disagreed that the system is robust and the remaining 4% was undeceive.

Figure 26 answered the question on the functionality of the hashing mechanism of the system collated from 100 users and showed that the hashing mechanism is functional with none disagreeing and undeceive.

Evaluation analysis of the developed system

Table 2. Evaluation of NAFCHAIN

No.	Questions	Yes	No	Undecided
1	Is the system secure	90%	5%	5%
2	Is the system user-friendly	95%	2%	3%
3	Is the response-time fast	98%	1%	1%
4	Is the system flexible	100%	0%	0%
5	Is the data integrity check effective	97%	0%	3%
6	Is the application robust	95%	1%	4%
7	Is the hashing mechanism functional	100%	0%	0%

Conclusion

Blockchain technology has shown immense capacity in the area of drug distribution chains through distributed shared ledger, deploying a smart contract to make the transactions on the network immutable, secure and transparent. In this study, a blockchain technology framework for addressing counterfeit drug circulation was proposed and Nigeria drug distribution system was the case study. Implementing the entire Blockchain technology requires enormous effort [33]. Therefore, the system is a proof of authority consensus which was designed and the implementation of an application was done in a simulated environment, demonstrating the deployment of smart contract in the automation of hashing mechanism. Due to advancements in technology, drug counterfeiting has also improved. Hence, the need for adopting a recent technology such as blockchain technology framework to winning the exhausting fight against counterfeit drug circulation in Nigeria. In order to accomplish the application system development, the smart contract was written in a

python programming language. Also, the model of a front-end interface was done using Flask (a Python web framework), HTML, and CSS. The system was tested using the following benchmark: security, usability, response time, flexibility, data integrity check effectiveness, robustness, hashing mechanism functionality. 90% of the users agreed that the system is secure, 95% of the users agreed that the system is user friendly, 98% of the users agreed that the system’s response time is fast, 100% users agreed that the system is flexible, 97% of the users agreed that the system’s data integrity check is effective, 95% users agreed that the system is robust, 100% of the users agreed that the hashing mechanism is functional.

References

[1] Nakamoto S. Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System; 2008. Available at: <https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf>

[2] Karamitsos I, Papadaki M, Al Barghuthi NB. Design of the Blockchain Smart Contract: A Use Case for Real Estate. *J. Inf. Secur.*, 2018;09(03):177–190. doi: 10.4236/jis.2018.93013

[3] Kamilaris A, Fonts A, Prenafeta-Boldú FX. The rise of blockchain technology in agriculture and food supply chains. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.*, 2019;91:640-652. doi: 10.1016/j.tifs.2019.07.034

[4] Bell L, Buchanan WJ, Cameron J, Lo O. Applications of Blockchain Within Healthcare. *Blockchain Healthc. Today*, 2017:1–7. doi: doi.org/10.30953/bhty.v1.8.

[5] Kikitamara S, Eekelen V, Doomernik J-P. Digital Identity Management on Blockchain for Open Model Energy System: 2017. Available at: https://www.ru.nl/publish/pages/769526/digital_identity_management_on_blockchain_final.pdf (accessed Jun. 12, 2021).

[6] Bryatov SR, Borodinov AA. Blockchain technology in the pharmaceutical supply chain: Researching a business model based on Hyperledger Fabric. *CEUR Workshop Proc.*,2019;2416:134–140. doi: 10.18287/1613-0073-2019-2416-134-140.

[7] Elisa N., Yang L, Chao F, Cao Y. A framework of blockchain-based secure and privacy-preserving E-government system. *Wireless Networks*, 2018. 10.1007/s11276-018-1883-0

[8] Baird L, Harmon M, Madsen P. Hedera: A governing council and public hashgraph network - The trust layer of the internet. *Whitepaper*, 2018:1–27. Available at: <https://s3.amazonaws.com/hedera-hashgraph/hh-whitepaper-v1.1-180518.pdf>

[9] Golosova J, Romanovs A. The advantages and disadvantages of the blockchain technology. In *2018 IEEE 6th Workshop on Advances in Information, Electronic and Electrical Engineering, AIEEE 2018 - Proceedings*, 2018, no. January 2021. doi: 10.1109/AIEEE.2018.8592253.

- [10] Zheng Z, Xie S, Dai HN, Chen X, Wang H. Blockchain challenges and opportunities: A survey. *Int. J. Web Grid Serv.*, 2018;14(4):352–375, 2018, doi: 10.1504/IJWGS.2018.095647.
- [11] NAFDAC. <https://www.nafdac.gov.ng/>; 2005. www.nafdac.gov.ng (accessed Feb. 02, 2021).
- [12] Jamil F, Hang L, Kim K, Kim D. A Novel Medical Blockchain Model for Drug Supply Chain Integrity Management in a Smart Hospital, 2019;1–32. doi: 10.3390/electronics8050505.
- [13] Sylim P, Liu F, Marcelo A, Fontelo P. Blockchain technology for detecting falsified and substandard drugs in distribution: Pharmaceutical supply chain intervention. *J. Med. Internet Res.*, 2018;20(9):1–12. doi: 10.2196/10163.
- [14] Musamih A, Salah K, Member S, Jayaraman R. A Blockchain-Based Approach for Drug Traceability in Healthcare Supply Chain; 2021. Available at: <https://covid19.elsevierpure.com/en/publications/blockchaininternet-of-things-iot-enabled-pharmaceutical-supply-ch-2> (accessed Jul. 18, 2021).
- [15] Fake Drugs: Health, Wealth and Regulation in Nigeria By Gernot Klantschnig and Chieh Huang; 1–18.
- [16] Francisconi M. An explorative study on blockchain technology in application to port logistics,” Master thesis TU Delft; 2017. Available at: <https://repository.tudelft.nl/islandora/object/uuid%3Ab1de98dd-f1a7-456a-b8cb-4d87dc2c4f9f>
- [17] Sadouskaya K. Adoption of Blockchain Technology in Supply Chain and Logistics; 2017. Available at: [https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/126096/Adoption of Blockchain Technology in Supply Chain and Logistics.pdf?sequence=1](https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/126096/Adoption%20of%20Blockchain%20Technology%20in%20Supply%20Chain%20and%20Logistics.pdf?sequence=1) (accessed Nov. 16, 2020).
- [18] Duan J, Zhang C, Gong Y, Brown S, Li Z. A Content-Analysis Based Literature Review in Blockchain Adoption within Food Supply Chain, 2020;17(5):1784. doi: 10.3390/ijerph17051784.
- [19] Ogbonna BO. Implications For The Goals Of National Drug Policy. *European Journal Of National Drug Distribution In Nigeria*, 2016;3(1):1–4.
- [20] Aigbavboa S. ScienceDirect ScienceDirect The The headache headache of of medicines ' medicines ' supply supply in in Nigeria : Nigeria : an an exploratory exploratory study study on on the the most most critical critical challenges challenges of of pharmaceutical phar. *Procedia Manuf.*, 2020;43:336–343. doi: 10.1016/j.promfg.2020.02.170.
- [21] Federal Ministry of Health. National Policy For Controlled Medicines And Its Implementation Strategies. Nigeria; 2017. Accessed: Jul. 16, 2021. Available at: <http://www.health.gov.ng/>
- [22] Omojokun J. Regulation and Enforcement of Legislation on Food Safety in Nigeria; 2013. Available at: https://cdn.intechopen.com/pdfs/44083/intech-regulation_and_enforcement_of_legislation_on_food_safety_in_nigeria.pdf (accessed Feb. 04, 2021).
- [23] Adedini AA, de Segun O, Oyetunde OO. Efficiency of mobile authentication service technology on phase 1 enabled drug products - a preliminary study. *Nig. Q. J. Hosp. Med.*, 2016: 4–7.
- [24] Uzochukwu CE, Chinedu-Okeke CF. Audience Awareness And Use Of Mobile Authentication Service (Mas) In Identifying Fake A Nd Substandard Drugs In Nigeria. Mgbakoigba, *Journal of African Studies*, 2017;7(1):46–66.
- [25] USP-PQM. Screening Medicines with the GPHF-Minilab TM. Promoting the Quality of Medicines; 2018. Available at: <https://www.usp-pqm.org/sites/default/files/pqms/article/monitoring-the-quality-of-medicines-2015-06.pdf>
- [26] Ogundipe S, Ajayi R. NAFDAC set to blank out fake drugs with TruScan, Black Eye technologies. Vanguard, 2011. Available at: <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2011/07/nafdac-set-to-blank-out-fake-drugs-with-truscan-black-eye-technologies>
- [27] Luminous J. 30 % drugs in circulation substandard, falsified. Vanguard News; 2020. Available at: <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2020/02/30-drugs-in-circulation-substandard-falsified/>
- [28] Joda AE, Amadi C, Adebayo OI, Maji YI, Uchem S, Olih H. Fake Drugs : A Survey of Healthcare Providers in Lagos State; 2017. doi: 10.4103/njbc.njbc.
- [29] Fatokun O. Curbing the circulation of counterfeit medicines in Nigeria Drug prices threaten the NHS. *Lancet*, 2016;388(10060):2603. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(16)32121-3.
- [30] Martin M. What is RAD Model? Phases , Advantages and Disadvantages; 2021. Available at: <https://www.guru99.com/what-is-rad-rapid-software-development-model-advantages-disadvantages.html> (accessed Sep. 27, 2021).
- [31] Kumar V, Hallqvist C, Ekwall D. Developing a framework for traceability implementation in the textile supply chain. *Open Access J.*, 2017;5(2). doi: 10.3390/systems5020033.
- [32] Oyinloye DP, Sen The J, Jamil N, Alawida M. Blockchain consensus: An overview of alternative protocols. *Symmetry (Basel)*, 2021;13(8):1–35. doi: 10.3390/sym13081363.
- [33] Alzahrani N, Bulusu N. Towards true decentralization: A blockchain consensus protocol based on game theory and randomness. *Lect. Notes Comput. Sci. (including Subser. Lect. Notes Artif. Intell. Lect. Notes Bioinformatics)*, 2018;11199 LNCS(May):465–485. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-01554-1_27.

